

Livelihood preservation of the fisherman in Lake Taal, Batangas: A basis on sardinella tawilis extinction

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to preserve the livelihood of the fishermen and to give an alternative livelihood despite the decline of Sardinella tawilis in Lake Taal, Batangas. This study is a mixed method, which employed a survey questionnaire and interview questions to figure out the possible alternative livelihood for their demographic assets and experiences. This study has 40 fishermen respondents from Tulo, Batangas, who have experienced the decline of Sardinella Tawilis. This study seeks to preserve and help the livelihood of the fishermen, to explore components of livelihood programs (poultry, seaweed gathering, tour guides, livestock production), components of controlling the decrease of Tawilis, the ability to meet long-term goals, and preparedness to meet an alternative livelihood program. In addition, the significant predictor of the researcher's reference is to gather information, knowledge, and understanding that would have good information in terms of both the fishing industry and alternative livelihood programs for the fishermen.

Keywords: *Sardinella Tawilis; Demographic assets; Experience; Alternative livelihood program.*

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Introduction

Over the years, the residents of Lake Taal, Batangas, were known for its delicacy, the Sardinella Tawilis, or most known as Tawilis. This is the only species of Sardinella that is solely found in freshwater. It was the main source of income of the resident fishermen in Lake Taal, Batangas, where the Tawilis is found (Willette et al., 2014). The International Union for Conservation of Nature, according to a 2019 report, declared the Sardinella tawilis as endangered due to overfishing and pollution as its main cause. This directly affects the livelihood of most of the residents living in the area who depended on fishing as their primary source of income (Guerrero, 2022). A “livelihood” is defined as one’s “means of support or subsistence” or the activities that economically support a person and his/her family. We are focused on providing opportunities for the working poor (in various occupations) to increase their income-generating capacity (Niles et al., 2021).

This research study aims to preserve the livelihood of the fishermen in Lake Taal, Batangas. With this paper, we can also formulate alternative livelihoods for the fishermen of Lake Taal while helping to control the excessive fishing of Tawilis and prevent its extermination, thus preserving its species. In the Taal Lake, they practiced fish cage farming, where fish cage operators stock their cages all at the same time, which could mean a glut in the market that can lead to a low market price. It could also be the other way around. When there is a shortage in supply, the price would increase tremendously, in which case only those who have the supply reap the benefits, and the consumers must pay a high price for what they buy.

The researchers aim to preserve their livelihood and create sustainable works despite the pervasive decline of the *Sardinella tawilis*. Where the researchers present some possible alternative livelihood opportunities for them, such as livestock production/raising, crop and livestock farmers, poultry, seaweed gathering, creating boats, factory workers, and tour guides. Specifically, it aims to create livelihood programs for the fishermen of the Taal Lake and help future researchers who would conduct the same study and provide sustainable results and information.

According to Faith (2019), The International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) has marked Tawilis, or “sardinella tawilis,” a freshwater sardine species found exclusively in the Philippines, particularly in Taal Lake, as an “endangered” species because of the alarming decrease in its population. There is a reason why the Tawilis is endangered, and there is an alarming decrease in its population due to overfishing, where even the newborn Tawilis has also been included.

Taal Lake’s *Sardinella tawilis*, or bombon sardine, the only freshwater sardine in the world, is now part of the International Union for the Conservation of Nature's (IUCN) endangered list due to several reasons, which include overexploitation, pollution, and competition and/or predation with introduced fishes (Camacho et al., 2022). The factors why Tawilis is now endangered may be attributed to overfishing, illegal use of active fishing gear like motorized push nets and ring nets, and the deterioration of water quality.

A means of creating a living is called a livelihood. It includes all a person’s abilities, possessions, money, and activities essential to ensuring the basics of life. A livelihood is sustainable when it enables people to cope with and recover from shocks and stresses such as natural disasters and economic or social upheavals and enhance their well-being and that of future generations without undermining the natural environment or resource base (International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies, 2020). The researchers will present alternative occupations to make income and activities to help and secure the necessities of all fishermen that they base their income on the fishing of *Sardinella tawilis*. The researchers aim to help the fishermen grow their livelihood and their income, not based on fishing. The researchers will propose alternative occupations like breeding poultry, livestock production/raising, poultry, seaweed gathering, and creating boats. Meanwhile, preservation is significant as it is considered the process of applying measures necessary to sustain the existing form, integrity, and materials of a historic property. Thus, the researcher will highlight the act of preservation of livelihood, where it will preserve the livelihood of the fishermen that affects the endangered species that cause the decreasing income of fishermen.

Related Literature

The IUCN Red List report conducted last February 28, 2017, and published in 2018 stated that since 1998, overfishing, the unlawful use of active fishing gear, the increased use of fish cages, and the degradation of Taal Lake's water quality have all contributed to a decrease in the Tawilis’ catch. It is reported that within the last ten years, there has been a minimum 50% decrease in the Tawilis harvest. The harvest of the Tawilis has been said to decline by at least 50 percent over the past 10 years. Because of this, the IUCN listed the Tawilis as endangered.

According to Faith (2019), The International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) has marked Tawilis, or “*Sardinella tawilis*,” a freshwater sardine species found exclusively in the Philippines, particularly in Taal Lake, as an “endangered” species because of the alarming decrease in its population. Overfishing, pollution, habitat degradation, and competition with other species in Taal Lake led to the decline of the Tawilis population by at least 50 percent. Fishing efforts using illegal gear that targets this species in the lake are increasing. The Tawilis harvest rose from 744 metric tons (MT) in 1996 to 1,120 MT in 1998 (Mutia et al., 2018). However, the catch suddenly dipped to 674 MT a year later in 1999 and continued to decline up to 71 MT by 2011, or about 89% reduction in only 12 years. Therefore, it can be assumed that the population has decreased, making it meet the “Endangered” criteria.

According to Lontoc (2019), Tawilis is famous for being the only *Sardinella* fish to live entirely in freshwater, and it can only be found in Taal Lake. Surrounding towns and cities consider Tawilis a staple food, and tourists love them deep-fried and served with Batangas bulalo. They find out that tawilis is one of the most special dishes because it can only be found in Taal Lake, Batangas. *Sardinella tawilis* survives in fresh water and is the only freshwater sardine species within the Philippines and possibly within the world. The *Sardinella* fisheries in Taal Lake form one in every of the foremost important freshwater resources within the country.

According to Mutia et al. (2020), Lake Taal is a source of livelihood and provides for more than 2,000 sustenance fishermen. Women, as a sector, constitute almost one-half of the economically active population in Lake Taal. Men and women performed different roles at different stages of fish capture or fish culture. In terms of their economic and social value, the participation of women in pre- and post-production activities is significant. The role of both men and women in fisheries is categorized into different works. Women have mainly a role and a supportive role to fishers, and men usually capture the fish.

According to Alba et al. (2018), the problem of overfishing and declining production of Tawilis has already been recognized, and several approaches have been done by the local government units and other concerned government agencies to address the declining Tawilis catch in the lake, including banning of active gears (e.g., motorized push nets), declaration of reserve area for Tawilis, restriction on the use of small-sized mesh nets, and recommendation for a possible closed season. Still, it is left uncontrolled or unregulated.

In a report by Pa-a (2019), according to the Department of Environment and Natural Resources, Tawilis will not become extinct and will continue to provide alternative livelihoods to affected fishermen. DENR will declare a preservation area. The DENR stated that they are paying close attention to the problem with Tawilis; they will not let it become extinct. They will implement a closing season for Taal Lake to make sure that Tawilis species will have time to breed. However, it is guaranteed that alternative livelihood interventions will be employed by DENR through partnering with concerned national government agencies like the Department of Social Welfare and Development and the Department of Labor and Employment, among others.

Another report by Jolombayan (2019) shows that according to Calabarzon Regional Development Council's Sectoral Committee on Economic Development (RDC-SCED), the action plan includes the implementation of a closed fishing season, based on a comprehensive scientific study, to allow the fish stocks to spawn. According to the reproductive biology study on Tawilis by the National Fisheries Research and Development Institute, the main research arm of the Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources (BFAR), a closed fishing season for Tawilis should be implemented from March to April. They implement an action or a closing season for the reservation of the Tawilis in every month from March to April to preserve the number of Tawilis before they catch it in May onwards.

Hilterman (2020) stated that Taal Lake is situated on the largest island in the Philippines, with a depth of 172 meters, and in the center of the lake is a dormant shield volcano named Taal Volcano. It is home to a diverse variety of unusual animal species, like the endangered freshwater squid and the only freshwater sardine in the country. The conservation area has been designated since the 1990s. Approximately 4,000 people who rely on fishing for their livelihood live around Taal Lake. In the late 1990s, they started to see a spike in the illicit farming of tilapia, a non-native plant.

To increase revenue from illegal fishing, these fish farmers designed cages where hundreds of fish are kept together. This generated serious concerns. The extreme amounts of fish in such a limited environment culminated in a loss of oxygen. In addition, the water became increasingly tainted due to elevated levels of organic fertilizer and human pharmaceuticals. The hog farms near the lake polluted the water with pig manure. This led to a mass of fish dying off.

The Pansipit River is so clogged with fish cages that the native species could no longer use it as a transportation path, which caused breeding cycles of the native species to be interrupted. The decrease of *Sardinella Tawilis* captured was induced by these two causes. According to Abad (2020), she stated that the Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources (BFAR) is anticipating the worst if fish cages were to be affected by the eruption of the Taal Volcano. The Calabarzon Regional Director said that as the volcanic activity continues, the lake's temperature and acidity will likely be fatal for the fish. The United Nations Environment Program (UNEP) listed the *Sardinella tawilis* as being endangered. The By-Law Enforcement agents are unable to enter the specified area as the volcano remains at Level 4. They cannot wait until the conditions are safe enough to return.

Sardinella Tawilis, locally known as Tawilis, is a freshwater sardine found exclusively in Taal Lake in Batangas province on the island of Luzon in the Philippines. *Sardinella tawilis* has different mesh sizes: 3.39 cm (10k), 3.05 cm (11k), 2.77 cm (12k), and 2.65 cm (12.5k). Little is known about their reproduction. It is known that the Taal population spawns during the months of April to July, when surface temperatures are highest. The lake's waters finally turned into freshwater because of major eruptions that virtually blocked it off from the sea in the 18th century. It appears that *Sardinella tawilis* is one of the rare extinct sea species that have transformed into exclusively freshwater species due to their captivity within the lake. The Lake Taal populations have been commercially fished for numerous decades, despite their vulnerable status. Tons of the fish are delivered to most of the main cities in the Philippines, where it is a highly popular eating fish. Typically, the species has its own tray or pile at nearby supermarkets and wet markets. It is one of the various types of fish that are sold in the nation, dried, salted, and dubbed daing. They are also commercially sold, smoked, and bottled in oil. Overfishing is a risk to the species because of several factors. A local extinction event will result in the extinction of the species, as is the case with all species that have a single population in a single site. Demand for Tawilis will rise in tandem with the Philippines' population growth, potentially leading to overfishing of the lake's stock population.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to preserve their livelihood and present alternative occupations that interact with the extinction of the *Sardinella Tawilis* within the livelihoods of the rural poor in Taal Batangas. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What kind of alternative occupations influence the extent to which those alternative occupations substitute fishing income?
2. Do the people of Taal, Batangas accept the alternative livelihood program?
3. What are the challenges encountered by the fishermen?
4. What livelihood needs can be proposed to preserve the extinction of *Sardinella Tawilis*?

Methodology

The researchers used a mixed-methods research design to accumulate the information and data by expressing their answers in fishing. Phenomenological research is a strategy where the use of bias is avoided. It commonly focuses on facts and personal experiences of the people involved. The study was conducted with the respondents residing in Taal, Batangas. These respondents were interviewed either via video chat or face-to-face. The researchers chose the place of implementation because it will give the researchers the needed information from fishermen.

This research study collectively consists of one barangay that accounts for a big percentage of the number of reptiles and amphibians in the lake. To validate the hypotheses, the work on the subject population is conducted at Barangay Tulo, Batangas. In 2019, the projected total population of households is 4,311. According to the Government of Batangas City, the total number of registered fishermen recorded

in 2019 is 1,245, the total number of registered motorized boats is 990, and the volume of production is 500 metric tons. This province is popular for Sardinella Tawilis, or freshwater fish, which is famous for different kinds of dishes using the Tawilis, and where most of the restaurants in Batangas and Tagaytay offer Tawilis dishes.

Figure 1. Map of Taal, Batangas, Philippines

A systematic sampling design (in every household) with a randomized start point based on the latest village census list (2019/2020) was used to select 30 households for the survey and 10 for the interview. This represents between 5-27% of the households in a village. Respondents for these households are heads of household or main income earners and often included both husband and wife who were interviewed and surveyed together (a total of 40 respondents). The researchers used convenience sampling, which is a type of non-probability sampling in which the researchers use subjects who are available to participate and the main respondents to gather data in the research study. Also, it does not take much time to find respondents and to be able to collect data with ease.

The research instruments used in this study are a survey questionnaire and an interview, where the researchers personally visited the place and communicated with the local government from the Municipal Hall of Batangas under the livelihood program for fishermen through virtual meetings. The collection of data has two parts: a survey questionnaire form and an interview question. The first part is a survey questionnaire, which is comprised of barangay, purok, and head of household; and for the second part, it contains questions regarding the study. The questionnaire has a total number of 10 items and a Likert scale with five choices. The second part is the interview questions, where it contains five items. The researchers ensure the proper use of research instruments to communicate to respondents to have enough information and to achieve expectations of our study.

The researchers used a survey questionnaire and interview questions to be answered by the fishermen, where a paper-pencil questionnaire was used for a selected number of respondents. The researchers used an interview, which consists of open-ended questions and consists of several items on which respondents can express their own opinion. The researchers used this type of approach to collect concrete and validity data in terms of transferring the audio sounds into transcribed format. The researchers provide a letter of approval to the barangay head to conduct an interview and survey with the fishermen around Taal Lake in Batangas. After the survey, the researchers tallied the responses of the respondents to each question.

This presentation summarizes the planning of a mixed-methods research approach for analyzing, interpreting, and presenting data gathered from survey questionnaires. To analyze qualitatively, the researchers reviewed the answer of each respondent and took note of possible similar answers. The following statistical tools for the interpretation of results according to sub-problems were used.

1. **Frequency.** It is the actual response to a specific item/question in the questionnaire where the respondent ticks his choice.
2. **Percentage.** This was used as descriptive statistics which describes a part of the whole.
3. **Mean.** The average of a data set is found by adding all numbers in the data set and then dividing by the number of values in the set. The Likert scale is to determine the level of awareness on selected algebra mathematical symbols.
4. **Standard Deviation.** It is a measure of the amount of variation of a set of values.
5. **Bar Graph.** A chart or graph that presents categorical data with rectangular bars with heights or lengths proportional to the values that they represent.

Results and Discussion

Figure 2 shows that majority of the respondents are males, which is 27 or 90%; while the remaining 3 or 10% is composed of females.

Figure 2. Demographic Profile

Figure 3 shows that 10% of the fishermen is 31, 35, and 49 years old respectively, while 7% are aged 30, 36, 38, 39, and 48 years old.

Figure 3. Age

Figure 4 shows that 25 or 83.3% of the fishermen is in the high school level of education, while the remaining is 5 or 17% fishermen took elementary level of education.

Figure 4. Educational Level

Figure 5 shows that 10 or 33.3% of the respondents have been a fisherman for 9-10 years, while the least of the respondents are fishermen for 5-6 years (7%).

Figure 5. Number of Years as a Fisherman

Sub-problem No. 1. What kind of alternative occupations influence the extent to which those alternative occupations substitute fishing income?

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of the Alternative Occupations

Alternative Occupations	Mean	Standard Deviation
Livestock Production	2.03	0.490
Crop Livestock Farmers	1.86	0.571
Poultry	3.00	0.000
Seaweed Gathering	0.67	0.479
Creating Boat	1.17	0.874
Factory Worker	1.83	0.747
Tour Guide	2.30	0.084

Table 1 shows that most of the respondents has an interest in poultry as an alternative occupation, with a computed mean of 3.00, while the least alternative occupation that does not meet the interest of the respondents is the seaweed gathering with a mean of 0.67. This shows that most respondents see the potential in poultry as an alternative occupation, while preventing the extinction of Tawilis.

Sub-problem No. 2. Does the people of Taal, Batangas accept the alternative livelihood program?

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of Accepting the Alternative Livelihood Program (n=30)

Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
A. They can cope with the new livelihood program in each barangay.	4.23	0.73	Agree
B. They find it difficult to adjust the way that they are not that familiar.	2.40	1.38	Disagree
C. They are happy because they have other sources of income.	4.27	0.78	Agree
D. Fishermen have high hopes for their future to become better.	3.77	0.77	Agree
E. It is not sustainable and beneficial for all.	2.00	1.17	Neutral
Overall	3.33	1.37	Neutral

Table 2 shows that in terms of accepting the alternative livelihood program in Taal, most fishermen said that they are happy because they have other sources of income. This table has an overall computed mean of 3.33, and a computed standard deviation of 1.37 with a verbal interpretation of Neutral.

Sub-problem No. 3. Do the other jobs provide enough benefits for a fisherman to consider them as a major source of income?

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics of Job Providing as a Major Income (n=30)

Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
A. It provides more benefits rather than in previous program.	3.33	0.55	Neutral
B. It only gives insufficient income and makes fishermen tiring.	2.73	1.01	Disagree
C. It is the best way to sustain everyday needs of the family.	3.57	0.73	Agree
Overall	3.21	0.85	Neutral

Table 3 shows that most respondents agreed that in terms of providing alternative jobs as a major income, alternative jobs is the best way to sustain everyday needs of the family. This statement has a mean of 3.57 from a total of 30 respondents.

Sub-problem No. 4. Does it provide enough benefits to the residents of Taal, Batangas?

Table 4. Descriptive Statistics of Providing Enough Benefits to Residents (n=30)

Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
It is much better than the previous program because it makes the lives of fishermen easy and comfortable at work.	3.33	0.71	Neutral
It can save time, and effort to build on every working hour.	3.90	0.88	Agree
They will have time for themselves to rest without worrying about the meals every day.	4.10	0.80	Agree
It gives them a peaceful environment.	3.73	0.78	Agree
It only makes it hard to work and adjust because of some factors.	2.33	1.06	Disagree
Overall	3.48	1.05	Neutral

Table 4 shows that in terms of providing enough benefits to residents, most respondents agreed that fisherman will have time for themselves to rest without worrying about the meals every day. This table has an overall computed mean of 3.48, and a computed standard deviation of 1.05 with a verbal interpretation of Neutral.

The goal of the research project is to preserve Taal Lake to safeguard the livelihood of the fishermen in the community. By putting together this paper, the inhabitants of Taal Lake will be able to establish a fishing livelihood program for the fishermen and contribute to the regulation of Tawilis fishing, thus avoiding extinction. Fish cage farming is being practiced at Taal Lake. Overfishing and pollution are two factors that may contribute to low market pricing. That may also be true when there is a lack of supply; the price will increase dramatically, and those who possess the supply will benefit from the situation. Additionally, the goods that the consumers buy are sold at a premium price to them.

Question 1: Does the extinction of Tawilis affect your life as fishermen?

According to the interview, the respondents said that the extinction of Tawilis has a big effect on their lives. The respondents said that there is not enough Tawilis to be caught, so they are really having a hard time making income for their families.

Question 2: How do you feel when you do not gather your target kilogram or number of Tawilis?

The respondents said that they are upset when they do not get the quota for catching Tawilis, unlike the past months or years. The respondents also mention that the number of Tawilis is very limited right now, and they just rely only on luck when they catch enough Tawilis.

Question 3: Do you ever think of catching other fish?

The respondents stated that they want to catch other fish, because sometimes if Tawilis is not enough, they have no choice but to catch other fish. The fishermen have no choice because they have families that need to eat after they finish their fishing day, while other respondents said that they do not want to catch other fish than tawilis because they are already used to catching tawilis ever since.

Question 4: What kind of work do you know other than fishing?

According to the respondents, when fishing is not enough to survive, they often get sideline work like farming and construction, so they can provide something for the needs of their families. The respondents also stated that construction and farming are easier for them who did not graduate from college because they have no documents to use to apply for better jobs.

Question 5: Do you ever try to ask for support from local government and local communities to provide substitute work? What kind of support you would ask?

The respondents said that some of them were provided with sari-sari stores by the local government to help them survive in their daily needs. Some of the respondents also received boats and some livelihood programs that will help them earn income to provide for their families. The researchers can conclude that there are advantages to helping the fishermen have an alternative job, and these advantages will be a big help for them to prevent the extinction of Tawilis.

The researchers found out that the extinction of tawilis in Taal, Batangas, is a very serious matter that needs attention. The researchers also found out that the reasons for Tawilis extinction are overfishing, illegal use of active fishing gear, increasing use of fish cages, and the deterioration of the water quality in Taal Lake. Helping the fishermen to have an alternative job can prevent the extinction of Tawilis in the meantime. Therefore, most fishermen accept the new livelihood work to sustain their everyday needs, and they have time for their families and themselves without worrying about everyday meals.

Most fishermen have no choice in pursuing other extra work like farming or even construction work to provide some income to their families. Some of them asked for some help from the local government to provide them with beneficial help because they are having a hard life in the extinction of the Tawilis. As a response, the local government offered livelihood programs like sari-sari stores and boats to help the fishermen provide income to their families despite the Tawilis extinction.

Conclusion

As the Tawilis *Sardinella*'s population continues to reduce, this study is enough basis for creating a long-term project that would provide fishermen in Taal, Batangas, with a means of subsistence. The fishermen may benefit from this study by exploring a variety of different options for earning a livelihood. These include things like growing animals or crops or raising cattle, keeping chickens, collecting seaweed, constructing boats, working in a factory, or leading tours.

The researchers found that the extinction of Tawilis in Taal Batangas is a very serious problem. During the investigation on the causes of the extinction of Taal Lake Tawilis, the researchers found out that overfishing is one of the elements contributing to their extinction. The rise in the illegal use of active fishing equipment, increasing usage of fish cages, and degradation of the water quality in Taal Lake are factors leading to the ultimate extinction of the species.

The researchers realized that it is essential to give the Tawilis fishermen an alternate source of income to preserve the life of Tawilis. It is clear, however, from the results that altering or creating an alternative program is not an easy job for them, but they are happy being given new alternative work because it is the best way to sustain the everyday needs of the family. In conclusion, the fishermen need to have urgent action to take; otherwise, a significant issue of unemployment might soon arise in their province. If there is a specific job that matches their skills, strengths, and expertise, they can adapt effectively to that task as well.

Recommendations

Since the fishermen choose poultry as an alternative livelihood, they should attend a vocational education course or training related to poultry so they will be knowledgeable for the new job and their effort would not be wasted. The researchers recommend that if the fishermen still doubt about accepting the alternative livelihood, they should have a fishing schedule to prevent the extinction of the Tawilis. For example, the fishing days for Tawilis can be Mondays to Wednesdays, while other days can be for working in a poultry as an alternative work.

The fishermen can try other different livelihood programs, so if Tawilis is not available, they still have income. Students and teachers should do their part to search for alternative things to prevent the extinction of Tawilis and give proper and enough information regarding the result of the extinction of any species and ways on how to help prevent the extinction. Local government units in Batangas should be aware and responsible in addressing the issues concerning fishing in their place so that the extinction of species may be prevented and would not cause hard life for the community. Fishermen should refrain from any illegal activities in fishing and observe regulations strictly regarding the quota in fishing.

This research, which will have a significant influence on fishing communities, must at least implement the assessment of the sustainability of the fishing resource and evaluate recommended solutions in terms of their possible effects on sustainability, then create and execute a basic fisheries sustainability program with the goal of increasing resource users' knowledge and comprehension of fisheries resource sustainability, and create and execute a fish resource and fisheries monitoring program to continuously analyze the condition and trajectory of fisheries. Future researchers should study the problem deeper and broader to be able to formulate more preventive measures that may solve the problem. The research will also help future researchers because these will indicate ideas and information about fishermen.

Figure 6. Sustainable Livelihood Framework Pertaining Sardinella Tawilis

The diagram demonstrates addressing livelihood possibilities from Sardinella Tawilis or alternative occupations program that could be implemented in terms of the livelihood, the structure and process, and livelihood outcomes. With these alternative occupations, it is expected that the income of the fisherman can be supported or sustained without depending to jobs based on Sardinella Tawilis.

Table 5. Sustainable Livelihood Plan

Category of Pertaining Livelihood	Output	Description
Presenting alternative livelihood program	Livestock Production Crop Livestock Farmers Poultry Seaweed Gathering Creating Boat Factory Worker Tour Guide	This will help them to choose what alternative livelihoods they want to try besides fishing. By this alternative work, the fishermen will know that they can also earn to provide for their families if the fishing is not enough for them.
Replacement of capture fisheries with aquaculture	It necessitates capital, capacity, and resources, as well as a fundamentally distinct livelihood activity that contributes differently to livelihoods. Support the creation of fishermen’s organizations / associations.	Give advice on how to enhance one's fishing skills. When feasible, improved fishing should focus on fishing production to decrease the danger of overexploitation, as well as research alternative commodities. Provide training and equipment for improved safety. Build capacity through organizational development training and provide proven strategies for establishing, financing, and running fishermen's organizations / associations.
Promoting development by supporting alternative livelihood	Support alternative livelihoods, including: pagtutuyo (drying fish), canning sardines, delivering in fish factory, and supplying to restaurants. Livestock and poultry support for micro and small enterprises. Encourage fishermen to focus on non-fishing livelihood activities.	To minimize project impacts on fisheries, encourage the establishment of alternative livelihoods. Where impacted groups and households already engaged in a variety of livelihood activities, and where a mix of resources, seasonal production levels, enough markets, and sufficient demand allows for adequate stabilization and resilience contributions typical of fisheries. Analyze and develop co-management initiatives, as well as organizational development and group strengthening in collaboration with the government and development partners (universities, non-government organizations).

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